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CULTURAL DIVERSITY: RIVER PEOPLE IN THE FACE OF THE STATE'S FOLKLORE DEMONSTRATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In an increasingly globalized and digital world, preserving cultural diversity becomes essential to maintaining identity and social cohesion. This paper explores the cultural diversity of riverside communities, with an emphasis on the folkloric manifestations present in these populations. Inspired by authors such as Luís da Câmara Cascudo, whose works detail the richness of Brazilian folkloric traditions, this study uses qualitative analysis to investigate how these cultural expressions are maintained and adapted over time, and their importance in preserving cultural identity and social cohesion. Cascudo notes that “folklore is the science that studies the facts and documents of popular culture, transmitted by tradition” (CASCUDO, 2012, p. 45), highlighting the relevance of traditions in maintaining cultural identity. The study reveals that folkloric traditions are fundamental to riverside life, providing a sense of belonging and historical continuity.